

POSTBUCKLING FAILURE OF CARBON-EPOXY COMPRESSION PANELS

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SUMMARY: The postbuckled failure of carbon/epoxy compression panels is studied experimentally and theoretically. Four different designs are considered each of which has significant postbuckled strength with a failure load more than twice the buckling load. The mechanisms which can initiate failure through stiffener debonding, prior to imminent explosive collapse, are postulated, taking account of the buckled mode shape. The specific mechanism which leads to failure in each of the particular four designs is identified from careful experiments with complete panels and also by suitably loading transverse strips cut from the panel to be tested. These component tests provide a quantitative guide to the magnitude of a stress resultant which will lead to debond initiation. This stress resultant can then be related to a compression failure load through an FE analysis of the postbuckled panel.

KEYWORDS: postbuckling failure, stiffened carbon/epoxy panels, axial compression

INTRODUCTION

Stiffened compression panels manufactured in carbon fibre composite can have a large reserve of postbuckled strength if the skins are thin ($b/t > 50$). Each of the four panel designs discussed in this paper has a ratio of failure load to buckling load greater than 2. For this strength margin between buckling and failure to be accessible to the designer, say to meet ultimate requirements, a method for predicting the failure load is needed.

Advanced finite element packages facilitate the prediction of displacements and stresses in a postbuckled panel. Even structures undergoing post-critical bifurcations or mode jumps can now be investigated successfully. However, a numerical strategy to predict the failure load of a stiffened panel still presents considerable difficulties, and this is especially true if there is no information from a laboratory test of the panel.

There are a number of reasons why failure prediction is difficult:-

- (i) Failure of these panels is invariably associated with separation of the stiffener from the skin, rather than as a result of in-plane material failure. There will be a number of locations in the panel where failure could be initiated, and in a number of possible ways. A priori the failure mechanism and location are not easily identified by analysis.
- (ii) The skin-stiffener assembly is a complex region involving a large number of variable quantities. The stiffeners may be co-cured or bonded and there will be resin rich

regions and areas where the plies will be curved. Also the flanges of the stiffener may be tapered in some way. All of these details, and of course the particular stiffener configuration, will govern the initiation and locus of the crack which will lead to stiffener debonding.

- (iii) There is a dearth of accumulated experimental evidence in the literature about how stiffener debonding is initiated. This is a consequence of the explosive and destructive nature of the failure which largely precludes any useful examination of the debris. Earlier researchers into postbuckling failure [2,3,4,5] who tested panels with I, blade and hat stiffeners all observed the explosive collapse and the stiffener separation, without identifying the initiating mechanism and its location. Ref. 6 noted "localised flange separation" in J stiffened panels before collapse but did not locate it with reference to the buckle pattern.

A number of workers, for example Ref. 7, have developed analytical techniques for calculating the stress distribution at the skin/stiffener interface. However these are idealised models which cannot reflect the idiosyncrasies of a particular case. They are helpful in regard to parametric studies, e.g. to observe the effect of the relative stiffnesses of the skin and the flange and web of the stiffener on the peak stresses [7].

This paper presents a study of the failure of four types of postbuckled panel having I, J and two forms of hat stiffener. In each case, knowing the buckle mode shape (from an FE analysis) the possibilities for failure initiation due to stiffener debonding are considered.

The results of some component tests which replicate some of the failure mechanisms are then considered before the experimental evidence from the complete panel tests are presented.

Finally a methodology for evaluating postbuckled failure loads is considered.

THE TEST PANELS

Each panel was made from unidirectional prepreg and had four stiffeners. The ends were potted and machined flat and parallel whilst the edges were unsupported. The panels were tested under axial load in a special purpose 250 tonne test machine which had been designed to have the high stiffness necessary for postbuckling studies. The panels varied in length, but each was long enough for there to be at least three half waves along the length when buckled.

Fig. 1: Four stiffener panel

I-Stiffened Panels

Material T300/914C. The panels had either co-cured or bonded stiffeners. An adhesive layer was present in each case, Fig. 2.

$$w = 610; b/t = 178/2 = 89$$

Fig. 2: I stiffener panel

J-Stiffened Panels

Material T800/924C. The panels were co-cured and incorporated an adhesive layer. The triangular region was filled with $\pm 45^\circ$ laminate, Fig. 3.

$$w = 903; \quad b/t = 270/3.25 = 83$$

Fig. 3: J stiffened panel

Hat-Stiffened Panels

Material T800/924C. The panels were co-cured and did not incorporate an adhesive layer. The filler material at the base of the webs was twisted adhesive tow.

There were two types of hat panel:

- Ht = stiffeners had tapered flanges.
- Hu = stiffeners had untapered flanges.

$$w = 610, \text{ stiffeners } 178\text{mm apart}$$

$$\therefore b/t \approx 138/2 = 69$$

Fig. 4: Hat stiffened panel (untapered)

BUCKLING MODES

In each case the skin buckled between the stiffeners, which remains essentially undistorted, even at 3 times the buckling load. Thus although a nonlinear FE programme was required for the postbuckling panel analysis the stress analysis of a local model of the skin/stiffener attachment could be treated as a linear problem.

Fig. 5(a): Mode shape for I and J stiffeners

Fig. 5(b): Mode shape for hat stiffeners

Fig. 5(a) shows the mode shape, for I and J stiffened panels. The buckling displacements are asymmetric with respect to a stiffener centre line. However the mode shape for hat stiffened panels, Fig. 5(b), is symmetric with respect to the centre line of a stiffener and this symmetry has an influence upon the possibilities for stiffener debonding, as shown in the next section.

STIFFENER DEBONDING MECHANISMS

In sympathy with the buckle mode shape the stress resultants in the panel will vary periodically having peak values at positions corresponding to nodal and anti-nodal (buckle peak) lines. Thus we might expect the initiation of stiffener debonding to occur at one of these positions.

I and J Stiffener Debonding

The I and J stiffeners behave in the same way. In each case the flange caps of the stiffeners provide a high torsion/bending resistance, leading to a significant moment transfer between the skin and the stiffener (Fig. 6). This moment, M_w , is a maximum at the buckle peak and, as discussed in Ref. 10, can induce debonding under the web. Also at the buckle peak the discontinuity in bending stiffness at the free edge of the flange can cause the skin to peel away from the flange (on the left-hand side in Fig. 6).

Fig. 6: Moments at an anti-node

A third possible failure mechanism exists on buckle nodal lines, where the bending moments M_w and M_f are zero, but the twisting moment in the skin, M_{xy} , is a maximum. The imposition of compatible shear strains by the skin on the stiffener flange gives rise to shear stresses τ_{yz} at the interface (Fig. 7). If these stresses are high enough debonding can ensue, as will be shown to be the case for the hat stiffened panels.

Fig. 7: Conditions on a node line ($M_x = 0$, M_{xy} max)

Hat Stiffener Debonding

Figs. 8(a) and 8(b) show conditions at adjacent buckle peaks on a hat stiffener.

Fig. 8: Moments at adjacent anti-nodes

In Fig. 8(a) the moment M_w is tending to peel the flange away from the skin starting at the inside of the stiffener. In Fig. 8(b) the skin tends to peel from the flange at its free edge due to the flexural stiffness discontinuity.

At the nodal line in a hat stiffened panel the twisting moment M_{xy} is a maximum and the diffusion of the load into the stiffener is associated with the interfacial shear stress τ_{xz} mentioned in 4.1.

COMPONENT TESTS

I and J Stiffeners

Figs. 6 and 8 show ways in which the moment stress resultants on anti-nodal lines might initiate debonding between the stiffener flange and the skin. In Ref. 10 methods were proposed for determining critical values of these bending moments. A "component test" using a strip cut from an I stiffened panel was loaded in a special rig to simulate the web bending which initiates debonding under the web. The onset of debonding from the free edge of the flange can be simulated by loading a strip in 4-point bending (see Fig. 9(b) for hat stiffener). Component tests for the J stiffened panel are the same as those for the I panel.

Hat Stiffened Panels

Figs. 8(a) and 8(b) show that at buckle peaks the loading is symmetric about the stiffener centre line but reverses in sign as we pass to an adjacent peak along the stiffener.

The loading in Fig. 8(a) is reproduced by the 4-point bending test in Fig. 9(a). If the specimen is turned over in the rig then the loading in 8(b) is produced, 9(b).

Fig. 9: Component tests for hat stiffened panels at the buckle crests

Debondings initiated by shear diffusion stresses on the nodal line are more difficult to reproduce in a simple component cut from the panel. An idea involving a torsional test is receiving attention.

These component tests, as well as providing guidance with respect to the critical values of stress resultants in the full panel test are also economical for parametric studies, Ref. 1.

PANEL TESTS

I Stiffened Panels

Refs. 9 and 10 reported results for some I stiffened panels. These panels initially debonded under the stiffener web at a buckle peak before explosive collapse. The correspondence between the micrographs at the failure site in the panel, and the component tests was remarkable, both in respect of the measured web bending moments at failure and the progression of the crack. In the co-cured case the crack went into the skin, whilst in the bonded case it remained in the flange (Fig. 7, Ref. 10). These panels typically buckled at about 11.5 tonnes and failed at 45 tonnes.

J Stiffened Panels

These larger panels buckled at approximately 30 tonnes and failed at a load of about 80 tonnes. Failure was initiated at a buckle crest when a crack propagated outwards from under the web (as in the case of the I stiffeners). A diagram of the failure is shown in Fig. 10.

Fig. 10: Failure initiation of J stiffened panel

During the panel test the moment measured in the web at the buckle crest was $M_w = 860\text{N}$ at failure. The mean value of the moment in the skin near the free edge of the flange was only $M_f = 40\text{N}$. This low value for M_f is confirmed by the FE analysis. M_f is changing sign rapidly in this region since there is a point of inflexion in the mode shape.

The 4-point bending component test showed that a moment, $M_f = 480\text{N}$, was required to cause a crack to propagate from the edge of the flange, into the skin, towards the web. The mechanism was very similar to that seen in Ref. 1. At the edge of the flange a crack forms in the outer 0° ply which, in this case, has been used to envelope the inner plies which have been dropped off to form the taper. As seen in Fig. 11 the crack passes the end of the next ply (90°) in the flange and enters the skin through its outer 0° ply. It then propagates towards the web in the $0^\circ/45^\circ$ interface.

Fig. 11: Failure of J component in 4-point bending

In contrast to the very successful replication of the I stiffened panel failure in the web bending component tests, the J stiffener component tests did not reproduce a web bending type of failure. The failure produced was the same as that first described in the four-point bending test. That is the failure originated in the 0° ply at the edge of the flange. Clearly surface 0° plies, both in the skin and also in the flange, are vulnerable to transverse bending caused by buckling. Strain measurements indicated that the web bending component test did not properly represent the buckle crest conditions because a too high skin bending moment was induced at the edge of the flange.

Hat stiffened panels

(a) Untapered stiffener flanges

In the panel test, and also in the component test, strain gauges were positioned on the stiffener webs to monitor the web bending strains (at the buckle crests in the panel). A component test in the form of Fig. 9(a) showed that a crack would propagate out under the flange when the web moment reached 165N. The FE analysis of the panel calculated that the test panel stiffeners would realise this moment when the panel load reached 48 tonne.

However, in the test of the panel, failure was initiated at 42.5 tonne, after buckling at 13.5 tonne. Also, significantly, failure occurred at a nodal line. The failure took the form of a local debonding of the flange. The crack was at the flange/skin interface, $\pm 45^\circ$, and propagated from the flange edge towards the web, Fig. 12.

Fig. 12: Flange debonding on the nodal line

Fig. 13 shows the shear strains measured in the panel skin on each side of a stiffener at two nodal lines. If the twisting moments compatible with these shear strains are applied to a local 2-D model, in an FE analysis, then a high interfacial shear stress, τ_{yz} , is found to exist.

Fig. 13: Shear strains in the skin near the flanges at nodal lines of a Hat panel

When failure of the panel occurred the moment in a stiffener web at a buckle crest was measured to be 159N. Extrapolating from these panel test results it would indicate that the panel would fail due to web bending at a panel load of about 46 tonne – a good agreement with the FE prediction. Fig. 13 also contains a theoretical point, again showing that the postbuckling behaviour is reliably predicted.

(b) *Tapered stiffener flanges*

It was expected that tapering the flanges would move the failure to the buckle crest, since the diffusion stresses would be alleviated at the nodal line. However, for the only panel where initiation could be identified the failure was the same as the case for the untapered flange i.e. a shear debonding opposite a nodal line. The failure load was 43.7 tonne.

CONCLUSIONS

Experiments show that in a stiffened compression panel, failure may be initiated at a nodal line or a buckle crest. This initial crack or delamination leads to stiffener debond and explosive collapse of the panel. However the analytical, a priori, prediction of a failure load would seem to be defeated by the complexity. Not only are there a number of possible failure mechanisms, but the location of crack initiation is not known.

It has been suggested that failure criteria can be established in some simple 2-D component tests which replicate the loading at particular locations in the postbuckled panel. These component tests not only indicate critical values of stress resultants, but also show the locus of the crack. This information is necessary for the complementary energy release calculations of fracture mechanics. These calculations would be done on a local 2-D model.

With an accumulation of evidence from various types of failure initiation it should be possible, either on the basis of component tests or because of design similarity, to identify the location and mode of failure without doing expensive panel tests. An estimation of the failure load can then be made using fracture mechanics, as in Ref. 11. The prediction of a postbuckled failure load for a new panel configuration would seem, at this time, to be very problematic without any guidance from experimental tests.

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